

Overview on Oral Thin Film of Diclofenac sodium: Efficient and Non- Invasive Form of Drug Delivery

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Abstract

In this article we discuss about Oral thin films (OTF) an new carrier for drug delivery are now gaining more attention due to its luring features, these thin films dissolve fast, are convenient and can potentially improve bioavailability of certain drugs by avoiding the first pass metabolism that essentially reduces the amount of drug which enter the systemic circulation, by directly supplying drug to systemic circulation, the dose at which drug are given can also be reduced according to their absorption. Diclofenac sodium a NSAID Non-steroidal and Anti-inflammatory active ingredient can be a potential candidate for oral thin films.

Keywords: oral thin films (OTF), polymer, Diclofenac sodium, buccal, sublingual.

I. INTRODUCTION

The drug administered via oral route being convenient, safe and economical is most preferred and used for years as a conventional choice despite bioavailability issues mostly due to solubility issues or excessive first pass metabolism. Novel drug delivery such as nano-technology despite successfully solving some of these issues they

are complicated dosage form and are not economical, there is need of simple dose forms which are simple and easily scalable and can be monetized effectively.[1]

Oral route being painless, easily administered, convenient and more compliant with patients compared to parenteral route which despite having excellent bioavailability is not the first choice in many cases due to its invasive procedure and requiring administration by a trained professional. Nevertheless, due to swallowing difficulty of oral dosage forms in many cases such as geriatric, paediatric, mentally challenged patients, coma patients, patients with paralysis, patients with nausea and vomiting issues etc. owing to these issues oral thin films has emerged as a preferred alternative showcasing better acceptability and convenience. [2]

Due to many of these issues mentioned above certain patients are hesitant to take solid oral dosage forms even the oral dissolving or oral disintegrating tablets fearing choking and asphyxia oral dissolving thin films has come forward as an alternative in these conditions. [3]

Oral thin films were first came into existence around late 1970s to solve the issue of swallowing difficulty produced by solid oral dosage forms in the late years oral thin films were called by various names such as wafer, mouth dissolving strips or films, mucoadhesive films, buccal films, thin films, oral strips, oral dissolving or disintegrating films soluble films etc. while some of these names may sound similar some films were designed to adhere to the mucosal or buccal cavity or to quickly dissolve in oral cavity and get absorbed through GI route but some of them were prepared to dissolve quickly for the drug to get administered through sublingual, mucosal or buccal route. [4]

Generally oral thin films are quick releasing films which dissolve quickly to release the active pharmaceutical ingredient in few seconds when come in contact with saliva which is possible because of the presence of polymers which are soluble in water used in making the films, further due to high membrane permeability of mucosal membrane owing to its thin membrane structure, high vascularity and adequate blood supply offers good systemic bioavailability. [5][6]

In such cases absorption of active ingredient, that is when active metabolite pass through mucosal layer into the bodily circulations is said to be directly proportional to the thickness of layer present from which we correlate the absorption spectra sublingual route > buccal route > palatal route. Additionally sublingual route in some drugs if applicable offers quick response owing to its bypassing first pass metabolism and directly supplying drug to systemic circulation, high permeability and adequate blood supply at the site of drug administration. [7]

NSAID are non-steroidal anti-inflammatory category of drugs, Diclofenac sodium being one of them has been used since 1970s to treat inflammatory and pain problems. Diclofenac works by interfering with enzymes like cyclooxygenase-I (COX-I) and cyclooxygenase-II (COX-II) from making prostaglandins which are agents that induce pain and inflammation. The active metabolite Diclofenac comes in sodium and potassium salt alternatives which are “diclofenac sodium” and “diclofenac potassium” of which diclofenac sodium being the mostly advised. It is commonly used for diseases and conditions like gout, rheumatoid arthritis, inflammation, migraine headache, joint pain also its topical formulations are used in conditions like musculoskeletal pain, conjunctivitis allergies, keratosis etc. Diclofenac even after being well absorbed by oral-GI route is not bioavailable to a good extent due to its excessive first pass metabolism, having half-life of around 1.5 to 2 h. [8]

After first pass metabolism bioavailability of diclofenac sodium is around 50%-55%, also food can cause delay in onset of absorption up to 1 to 4.5 hrs despite no change in extent of absorption and reduce peak plasma concentration around 20%. [9][10]

II. ORAL MUCOSAL INVOLVEMENT IN DELIVERY OF ORAL THIN FILM (OTF)

Orla mucosal thickness is around 100-200 micrometer, mucus fluid mostly composed of 90%-99% also contain several other components such as nucleic acid, glycoproteins, enzymes, electrolytes is released by submucosal layer. The lobules that make up the salivary glands release saliva from the salivary duct close to the submandibular teeth and sublingual canals. Most frequently, smaller salivary glands are present around the

mucosal lining of lips and cheeks. Saliva is released by salivary gland in about 1-2ml/min rate. water, mineral salts salivary amylase, immunoglobulins, mucus etc are salivary components. The oral mucosa is protected by mucin and saliva as they act as a barrier for oral mucosa. [11][12]

There are two different parts of mucosal epithelial membrane, the lipophilic stratified epithelium and the gap between cells which is hydrophilic. [3] The permeability capabilities of oral mucosa are not greater than intestinal mucosa but is better than epidermis, it's around 4 to 4000 times of the skin.[12] But the if taking surface area in consideration surface area of oral mucosa < skin < GI tract. [13] In oral mucosa gingival and hard palate are keratinized epithelia which are comparatively water impermeable and display barrier like function due to the presence of acyl-ceramides and ceramides lipids. Whereas sublingual, soft palate and buccal compared to keratinized region contains less ratio of glycosyl ceramides and cholesterol sulphates a type of neutral polar & lipid, which makes non-keratinized epithelia more water permeable. Composition of both epithelia is about 50 and 30 % of the total mucosal surface area. [14]

Figure 1. human oral cavity (modified from [14])

Table1. parameters of mucosa [14]

Tissue	Thickness in milli meter	Surface area (cm ²) ± SD	Blood flow	Time of residence	Permeability
Floor of mouth-sublingual (NK)	100-200	25.5 ± 4.5	12.4	Low	High
Buccal (NK)	450-600	45.5 ± 2.8	20.5	Medium	Medium
Palatal (K)	220-250	18.8 ± 2.0	7.2	High	Low

Paracellular (intercellular) that is movement of components between the cells, facilitate penetration of hydrophilic molecules because of polar nature intercellular spaces and transcellular (intracellular) which is movement of components through the cells itself, facilitate penetration of hydrophobic molecules or molecule with higher partition coefficient because of the lipophilic nature of cell membrane, these are the two main pathway of absorption via mucosal epithelium. [12][15]

Figure 2. Mucosal epithelium pathways [3]

III. COMPONENTS OF ORAL THIN FILM

- Active substance
- Film polymer
- Plasticizer
- Flavouring agent
- Sweeteners
- Super disintegrant
- Saliva stimulant
- surfactant

3.1 Active ingredients that could be used in OTFs:

Dissolution of active ingredient is important for absorption process, drug or active ingredient primarily gets absorbed through passive diffusion and non-ionized form of drug display lipid soluble properties that is lipophilicity which helps penetrates through cell membrane. Partition coefficient determines lipophilicity of the drug which is usually proportional to the absorption, although lipophilicity is important, solubility plays an important role in absorption, if the active ingredient is more lipophilic by nature its ability to dissolve in water decreases significantly obstructing absorption process so there should be balance between Lipophilic and hydrophilic (solubility) nature of the drug. In conclusion partition coefficient, ionisation, log p, molecular weight, amount of active to be administered these all play a significant role in selection of active ingredient for OTFs. [15][16][17] For sublingual delivery of drug through OTF the pKa should be >2 for active ingredient which are acidic in nature and $10 <$ for the active ingredients which are more basic in nature. [18] The log p value should range between 1-5, the molecular weight should be less than 600.[19]

Table 2: Marketed sublingual formulations and their physiochemical properties [7][18][20]

Active molecule	pKa	Aqueous solubility	Mol.wt. g/mol	Log p	Brand name	Application	Dosage	Dosage (mg)*
Buprenorphine	8.5/10	Not soluble	467.6	4.9	Subutex®	Opioid analgesic	Tablet	2, 8
Fentanyl citrate	8.4	0.024mg/ml	336	8.4	Subsys®	Opioid analgesic	Spray	50,100,200ug
Nitroglycerine	6.3	1.8mg/ml	227	-5.6	Nitrostat®	Angina	Tablet	0.4 ,0.6
Buprenorphine hydrochloride + naloxone	8.5/10 ,7.9	17mg/ml, 73mg/ml	467.6, 327.4	4.9,2	Suboxone®	Narcotic opioid antagonist	films	8/2, 2/0.5

The dose range for the therapeutic effect should not exceed 40 mg and must be soluble and stable in saliva. [21] Diclofenac sodium a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) having log p value of 4.51, pka value of 4.15 and molecular weight of 318.13g/mol. [22]

Figure 3. Diclofenac sodium structure

Considering these values Diclofenac Sodium could be a candidate for sublingual OTFs as a sublingual spray of diclofenac is already patented with US patent (no: US 9,855,234 B2) Jan. 2, 2018.

Table 3: oral thin film components [1] [3] [4] [7] [20][21] [23]

Component	Examples
Active substance	Timolol maleate, Natamycin, phenylephrine, ondansetron, Buprenorphine hydrochloride + naloxone, Loratadine, Montelukast sodium, Acetazolamide, Ofloxacin, Levofloxacin, Naphazoline HCl, ropinirole hydrochloride, triclosan, sertraline, metoclopramide hydrochloride, telmisartan, Sumatriptan succinate, omeprazole, Dorzolamide HCL.
Film-forming polymer	Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose E5&E15, Gelatine, Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), Hydroxypropyl cellulose, croscarmellose sodium, PVP, Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), Polyethylene oxide, Pullulan, sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, Pectin, methylcellulose, Chitosan, Sodium alginate, Carrageenan, Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC).
Plasticizer	Tributyl citrate, Glycerine, malic acid, PEG 400, propylene glycol, sorbitol, triethyl citrate, and triacetin, etc.
Flavouring agents	Liquorice root, Vanilla, peppermint, clove, lemon, peach, raspberry, orange, chocolate, strawberry etc.
Sweeteners	aspartame, mannitol, sorbitol, saccharin, sucralose, sucrose, acesulfame-K, cyclamate and neotame.
Super-disintegrant	Sodium starch glycollate, Crosspovidone, Polacrillin potassium.
Saliva stimulant	Fumaric acid, Tartaric acid, succinic, Ascorbic acid, citric acid, lactic acid.
Surfactants	Tween 80, polysorbate, poloxamer 407, DMSO, Transcutol®.

IV. CLASSIFICATION OF THIN FILMS

1. Quick release
2. Mucoadhesive sustained-release wafers
3. Mucoadhesive thin films

Table.4 OTF classification [3]

Parameters	Quick release	Mucoadhesive sustained-release wafers	Mucoadhesive thin films
Layer	Single layer	Multilayer	Single or multilayer
Area cm ²	2-6	2-4	2-7
Thickness	10-100mm	50-250	50-250
Excipients	Water-soluble	Low solubility	Water-soluble
Area of application	Sublingual, buccal	Gums, buccal	Buccal, gingival
Dissolution	60s	7-9 h	Minutes
Area of effect	Systemic or local	Systemic or local	Systemic or local

V. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF OTF COMPARED TO OTHER CONVENTIONAL DOSAGE FORMS

5.1 Advantages [4][11][24][25][26] -

- Formulation does not require water
- Easy to use
- Convenient
- Easy usage specially for paralysed, mentally challenged, disabled persons
- Low dosage required
- Travel friendly
- Increased bioavailability
- Reduce dose dumping
- Less dose dependent side effects
- Rapid onset of action
- Expanding market size of OTF
- Rapid dissolution and disintegration
- Less fragile than oral disintegrating tablets ODT
- Direct absorption to systemic circulation
- Good stability compared to liquid dosage
- Convenient for paediatrics, geriatric, bedridden patients to avoid risk of choking leading to asphyxia.

5.2 Disadvantages [4][11][24][25] -

- Requirement of specialized packaging equipment
- Some drugs can cause irritation as their pH does not suit oral cavity
- Not suitable for drugs with high dose
- Hygroscopic nature of the formulation can cause issue for shelf life and preservation thus precaution is advised
- Not registered in pharmacopeia

- Due to less availability of manufacturing facility large scale manufacturing process is restrained and costly
- Longer drying process takes time and effect production rate
- Not all drugs are thermostable to be formulated for OTF

VI. FORMULATION METHODS OF ORAL THIN FILMS

6.1 Solvent/ semisolid casting method-

As this process is a straightforward, inexpensive in processing, convenient in usage and scalability therefore it is the most preferred technique for formulating Oral Thin Films (OTF). In this process a stirrer is used to mix active component with film forming polymer and other components like plasticizer, sweetening agent etc, to create a homogenous mix, the solution is then transferred into a petri plate and stored for about 18-48 hrs for drying at room temperature or for a shorter duration at 40°C–45°C in the hot air oven. The prepared film is then trimmed into the dose accurate pieces on basis of therapeutic ingredient present in them. Similarly in the semisolid method a more viscous polymer solution having semisolid consistency is prepared and placed in an appropriate mould to be dried to make films, prepared films are sliced into the appropriate proportions according to the amount of drug present. [3][6]

While performing solvent casting air entrapment in the solution is a point to consider as air bubbles may get entrapped while mixing slow mixing and degassing is recommended to obtain a smooth film without air pockets. In industrial setup films are prepared rolled out and stacked together and stored to be divided into pieces, but exposing film to outside environment for a long period can damage them instead films should be packed as early as possible to protect them from environmental damage and maintain its stability. [4]

Fig 4: mechanical figure depicting commercial solvent casting of thin films [4]

6.2 Hot melt extrusion method-

Hot melt extrusion method (HEM) is a formulation method often used to prepare transdermal patches, films and especially for films which do not need organic solvent although there are very few literature mentioning use of this method for production of polymeric films, in this method a formulation mixture that is active ingredients polymer and other excipients are subjected to extreme heat via extruder which melts all the components making them into homogenous a mixture and shaping them through moulding process. As the process subject the active component to high heat heat-labile substances are not suited for this method.[3][4]

6.3 Rolling technique-

In this approach, water or water and alcohol combinations are frequently utilized as solvents. Only a tiny amount of solvent is used to dissolve the active chemical and other excipients with high shear force. The roller gets the solution and then rolls it out. After removing moisture, dried films are made into dosage suitable sizes for distribution.

6.4 Solid dispersion extrusion-

Drugs and immiscible ingredients are combined to create solid dispersions. Dies/ orifices mould the solid dispersion applying pressure and heat in form of films [7]

VII. EVALUATION OF ORAL THIN FILM

7.1 Thickness-

Thickness of oral thin film can be measured by screw gauge and other thickness measuring tools like vernier calliper as the thickness uniformity of is important in thin films and can affect dose distribution and so drug uniformity as well. Measurement of thickness should be taken from all corners and centre of the film as well, around 4-6 films should be measured and recorded. Optimal thickness of thin films could be around 5-1000 μm . [21]

7.2 Tensile Strength-

Maximum amount of stress applied on a film till it breaks that threshold is its tensile strength to calculate tensile strength applied stress at the point of tear is divided by the thickness multiplied by width.[7]

$$\% \text{ Tensile strength} = \frac{\text{Load at failure} \times 100}{\text{Thickness of film} \times \text{film width}}$$

7.3 Percent Elongation-

Strain applied to film as the result of stretch, that strain leads to deformation in the film result in change in length known as elongation strain. Plasticizer directly affect the elongation, higher the amount greater will be its elongation. [7][21]

$$\% \text{ Elongation} = \frac{\text{Change in length} * 100}{\text{Initial length}}$$

7.4 Folding Endurance-

Folding endurance as the name suggest checks the endurance of the film till it breaks, the film is folded numerous times and the number of folds are noted till it breaks, key point to note is that film should be folded repeatedly from a single place.[7]

7.5 Weight variability-

About 1x1 or 2x2 cm² of film samples are cut from each formulation and the weight of these samples are measured and noted, then weight variation is calculated.[3]

7.6 Surface pH-

The pH film is a critical parameter for its solubility and to determine if there is irritation caused due to pH difference in the mucosa and film, for determining pH film is submersed in about 0.5 to 1ml of deionized water in a petri plate for around 50 sec and then pH is measured with the help of pH meter or pH paper. [1]

7.7 Moisture absorption capacity-

High humidity conditions are maintained to conduct this test, film sample are weighed and then put in desiccator which contain AlCl₃ Aluminium Chloride exposed to moisture for about 2-3 days then weighed again to calculate % moisture absorption. [3]

% Moisture absorption capacities = (Initial Weight - Final Weight) × 100 /Initial Weight

7.8 Content uniformity-

To calculate the drug content prepared film is dissolved in the solvent and sonicated to ensure its dissolution, after that solution is passed through Whatman filter paper, resultant solution was then diluted with 6.8 pH buffer, the diluted solution is then checked for drug content through UV spectroscopy and absorbance was noted, content uniformity was then calculated with the help of regression equation. [1] The procedure would be carried out in pair of three and average value was recorded. [20] further the range of content uniformity should be in between 85-110%. [21]

7.9 In Vitro Disintegration Time-

In vitro disintegration could be performed disintegration apparatus and disintegration time till all the films were completely disintegrated was recorded, based on EU pharmacopeial specifications for oral dispersible films, three 4cm² were dispersed in in pH 6.8 solution at 37°C, disintegration time was recorded via stopwatch and mean disintegration time was noted.[27]

7.10 In Vitro Dissolution-

There are not as such standardised testing procedure for Oral thin Films, the dissolution test could be performed either by USP I dissolution apparatus which is basket apparatus with 300ml of pH 6.8 buffer at 37 ± 0.5 °C with or with USP V dissolution apparatus which is paddle over disk with the same pH temp and rpm mentioned above but with 900ml solvent both of these are done in rpm of 50. Film was placed in apparatus for dissolution and about 1 ml or 5 ml sample solution was taken from the apparatus depending on which is used and the same amount of solvent was added back to maintain the sink condition, sample is taken every 2 minutes or 5 min for 30 to 60 min depending on the formulation requirement. The sample at different point of time were analysed for the absorbance at their lambda max and amount of drug release was calculated by putting absorbance values in the regression equation. [1][21][27]

7.11 In Vitro Drug release using Animal Tissue (Ex Vivo)-

These studies are conducted using animal tissues with the help of Franz diffusion cell. The tissue is placed between both the compartments the film was placed in donor compartment with about 1-2 ml of pH6.8 buffer solvent and receptor compartment were also filled with the same solvent. At different determined time intervals samples were taken and drug permeated was measured with UV spectrometer. Another sample were taken for comparison with 1miligram of active component.[2]

VIII. FUTURE PERSPECTIVE AND OPPORTUNITIES IN OTF

OTFs are becoming more and more accepted as a newer alternative to conventional form of drug carrier in pharmaceutical sector, as the diversity of biocompatible polymers and production technology that have allowed for the development of several OTF varieties. A lot of work has gone into creating oral thin films that can be administered via buccal, sublingual, transdermal and even ocular route. Out of these films the use of oral thin films for medication delivery via the buccal and sublingual route has attracted a lot of interest lately, as these films contain water soluble polymers when the films come into contact with saliva, they start to disintegrate and dissolve within seconds, followed by rapid absorption and instantaneous bioavailability. Due to these properties of OTF pharmaceutical industries have shown significant interest in them and are working towards patenting this technology as per their product requirements. Unlike conventional dosage forms these films neither need accessibility to water or help of professionals for administration. It is important to distinguish OTFs from mucoadhesive buccal films, which are intended to stay on the surface of the mucosa for longer duration and extended drug release. [3][25]

Fig 5: estimated market share of oral thin films [3]

The development of oral thin films as a drug delivery alternative has been prompted by a number of unfavourable issues with traditional dosage forms, including patient non-compliance, reduced bioavailability, and administration difficulties. Both new and renowned pharmaceutical businesses have shown interest in it and are looking forward to invest in development of various kinds of thin films. Although future looks bright, for oral thin films to be commercialized at a larger scale there is still a lot of work to be done in developing, standardizing and regulating this technology. [4]

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